

Synthesis, Growth and Characterization of Zinc Doped Nonlinear Optical Material of 4 - methoxy - 4' - dimethylamino benzylidene aniline

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Abstract

In recent years the interest in synthesizing of organic and semi organic materials with charge correlated and highly delocalized π -electron states and growing them as single crystals has increased considerably, since very large nonlinear optical susceptibilities have been measured in some of the materials to utilize them for various applications. Synthesis, growth and characterization of a novel third order nonlinear optical material, 4-methoxy-4'-dimethylamino benzylidene aniline doped with zinc are reported for the first time. The structural perfection of the grown crystal is analyzed by X-ray diffraction. The functional groups present in the synthesized material are investigated by FTIR and FT-Raman spectral analyses. The placement of the protons is determined using HNMR spectrum. The range and percentage of optical transmission were ascertained by recording UV-VIS-NIR spectrum. Thermal and mechanical properties are also studied. Dielectric study shows that the dielectric constant of the crystal varies with frequency and temperature. The third order nonlinear optical absorption coefficient of the crystal is determined by the Z-scan technique.

Keywords: Organic Compounds, Crystal Growth, Dielectric Studies.

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